

From virtual data to real insights: an overview of simulation-based inference for scientific discovery

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ABSTRACT

Virtual data generated from accurate, physics-based simulations has emerged as a powerful tool for training and validating machine learning models across diverse scientific fields. However, this approach comes with potential pitfalls: if simulated and real-world data diverge significantly, the resulting models may underperform when confronted with real tasks. This semantic gap highlights the need for robust domain adaptation strategies, which systematically reduce the differences between synthetic and real domains. By leveraging increasingly realistic simulations and refining domain-adaptation techniques, we can accelerate the discovery of new insights and applications, from advancing our understanding of the cosmos to improving patient outcomes in medical imaging trials. This contribution illustrates how virtual data serves as a catalyst for scientific progress while also highlighting best practices to ensure results that are reliable, uncertainty-aware, and transferable.

1. BACKGROUND AND PURPOSE

1.1. *The rise of simulation-based learning in science*

The integration of simulations with machine learning (ML) is emerging as a transformative approach across scientific disciplines. Virtual data, generated through

physics-based simulations, now serves as a cornerstone for training and validating ML models in numerous fields (see e.g., a thorough review by [K. Cranmer et al. 2020](#)). In particle physics, for instance, simulation frameworks enable researchers to predict complex particle interactions in high-energy collisions (e.g., [J. Brehmer 2021](#); [H. Bahl et al. 2024](#); [R. Mastandrea et al. 2024](#)). In astronomy, ML models increasingly leverage high-fidelity simulations that reproduce the complexity of observations to perform highly efficient cosmological and astrophysical parameter inference through simulation-based inference (SBI; e.g., [R. Legin et al. 2021](#); [X. Zhao et al. 2022](#); [G. Khullar et al. 2022](#); [M. Aubin et al. 2023](#); [D. Barret & S. Dupourqué 2024](#); [C. Hahn et al. 2024](#); [P. Iglesias-Navarro et al. 2024](#)). In medical physics, virtual patients and trials have revolutionized research methodologies. Here, simulations accelerate the development of diagnostic tools while addressing ethical concerns and logistical constraints inherent in clinical research (e.g., [A. Wehenkel et al. 2023](#); [I. Caspi et al. 2023](#); [E. Katsoulakis et al. 2024](#)).

The fundamental advantage across all these domains is that simulations can provide abundant and optimal ground truth labels, which are rarely available with real-world data (e.g., [K. Cranmer et al. 2020](#)). This labeled virtual data provides a strong basis for building ML models that can uncover useful information from complex systems.

1.2. *Bridging the domain gap: from simulation to reality*

Despite their usefulness, there is an important caveat with simulation-based approaches: they rely on the assumption that simulations truly represents the real world. While significant efforts are made to create realistic simulations, computational models inevitably simplify the complexity of natural phenomena. This discrepancy creates a “domain gap” between simulated and real data, potentially undermining the performance of ML models when deployed in real-world settings (e.g., [A. Torralba & A. A. Efros 2011](#); [Y. Ganin et al. 2016](#); [J. Tobin et al. 2017](#)). This poses a fundamental challenge for ML pipelines, which often converge on domain-specific solutions during optimization. Experimental evidence has repeatedly demonstrated performance degradation when models trained on simulated data are applied to real-world scenarios (e.g., [A. Ćiprijanović et al. 2020](#); [F. Belfiore et al. 2025](#)). This problem is well-recognized in computer vision, where numerous challenges have been organized specifically to address the simulation-to-reality gap (e.g., [M. Wang & W. Deng 2018](#)).

In ideal circumstances, one might train models using a mixture of simulated and real data, or fine-tune simulation-trained models with real data. However, the absence of ground truth labels in real data often prevents such straightforward solutions. Domain adaptation techniques offer promising alternatives (e.g., [H. Guan & M. Liu 2022](#); [S. Kumari & P. Singh 2024](#)), with domain adversarial neural networks (DANNs) emerging as a particularly effective approach for aligning features across domains without requiring labels in the target domain (e.g., [Y. Ganin et al. 2016](#); [E. Tzeng et al. 2017](#)).

Simulations (training) — Observations (inference)

Figure 1. A sketch of the proposed framework for SBI using normalising flows and domain adversarial training. The embedding network extracts domain-invariant summary statistics from input data (e.g., spectra, images, datacubes), which are used by a conditional flow to perform inference with associated uncertainties.

2. METHODS

We outline a general framework for leveraging simulated data and ML methods to derive insights across scientific disciplines, with emphasis on addressing the domain gap between simulation and reality and on achieving probabilistic outputs for degenerate problems.

2.1. *Ensuring simulation fidelity: metrics and diagnostics*

The effectiveness of SBI relies on the alignment between simulated and real data. Rigorous validation protocols are essential to ensure that synthetic data captures the key characteristics of real-world observations, even before applying domain adaptation techniques. For instance, noise patterns, signal-to-noise ratios, and, for vision tasks, power spectra should exhibit consistent distributions across both domains. In specific scientific domains, dedicated diagnostics can be used to assess the fidelity of simulations (e.g., P. Lemos et al. 2023; M. Reza et al. 2024; C. Bracci et al. 2025). In medical imaging, for instance, the distributions of radiomic features should closely match between synthetic and clinical images to ensure that insights remain transferable (e.g., A. Traverso et al. 2018).

These metrics not only validate simulation quality but also identify specific areas where domain adaptation may be necessary.

2.2. *Domain adversarial training for robust transfer*

DANNs address the challenge of transferring knowledge from simulated to real data. These networks consist of three key components: a feature extractor, a label predictor, and a domain classifier. The feature extractor aims to learn representations that are both informative for the primary task and invariant across domains (e.g., Y. Ganin et al. 2016; H. Guan & M. Liu 2022; S. Kumari & P. Singh 2024). The innovation of DANNs lies in their training objective: the feature extractor is trained to maximize confusion in the domain classifier while minimizing error in the label predictor. This adversarial approach forces the network to learn domain-invariant features, i.e., representations that cannot be easily identified as belonging to either the simulated or real domain (e.g., K. Kamnitsas et al. 2016; A. Čiprijanović et al. 2020; F. Belfiore et al. 2025).

Interestingly, DANNs can be integrated with various neural architectures (e.g., M. Wang & W. Deng 2018; L. Chen et al. 2024; Y. Li & Y. Wu 2024; Z. Chen et al. 2025). By aligning the distribution of embedding features across domains, these methods ensure that estimates derived from simulated data remain valid when applied to real observations.

This alignment occurs without requiring labeled data in the real domain (e.g., Y. Ganin et al. 2016), making the approach particularly valuable for applications where ground truth is unavailable.

2.3. *Neural posterior estimation*

Many scientific problems are inherently degenerate, meaning that different combinations of parameters can produce nearly indistinguishable observable outcomes. To address this, researchers have long relied on simulated data within Bayesian frameworks, where synthetic datasets are used as inputs to Monte Carlo methods to enable rigorous uncertainty quantification (see e.g., D. Sivia & J. Skilling 2006).

Standard ML methods, by contrast, often fail to capture the full extent of uncertainty. SBI with normalizing flows (NFs) offers a powerful alternative. It combines the flexibility of neural networks with the probabilistic rigor of Bayesian inference, and its amortized nature allows fast inference after training by sampling from simple distributions to reconstruct complex posteriors (e.g., [K. Cranmer et al. 2020](#); [G. Papamakarios et al. 2021](#)). NFs work by transforming simple probability distributions (typically Gaussian) into complex, potentially multi-modal posteriors through a series of invertible transformations (e.g., [C. Hahn et al. 2024](#); [P. Iglesias-Navarro et al. 2024](#); [E. Katsoulakis et al. 2024](#)). In conditional settings, the object of interest, such as a spectrum, image, or data cube, acts as a condition for the flow (e.g., [G. Papamakarios et al. 2021](#)). Because these inputs are often high-dimensional, an embedding network first extracts relevant summary statistics, which are then passed to the flow to generate the conditional posterior (e.g., [P. Lemos et al. 2023](#); [N. Candebat et al. 2024](#)).

Importantly, the embedding network in conditional NFs can be combined with a DANN to ensure domain invariance ([Ginolfi et al., in preparation](#)).

3. RESULTS EXAMPLES – PRELIMINARY APPLICATIONS IN ASTRONOMY

Recent work has demonstrated the effectiveness of SBI in astronomical research. In [C. Bracci et al. \(2025\)](#), we showed that ML models trained on carefully calibrated simulations could successfully predict properties of real galaxies observed with the Very Large Telescope, classifying with high accuracy interstellar nebulae into HII regions, planetary nebulae, and supernova remnants. Looking toward future instrumentation, in [M. Ginolfi et al. \(2025\)](#), we highlighted the importance of simulation-based pipelines in preparing for new observational capabilities. In particular, we trained a multi-task neural network to achieve optimal performance in deriving physical properties (e.g., redshift, stellar mass and star formation rate) from simulated galaxy spectra for the upcoming MOONS instrument. In [F. Belfiore et al. \(2025\)](#), we addressed the challenge of domain adaptation in galactic spectroscopy by implementing a DANN to align feature distributions between simulated and observed sets of galaxy emission lines. Our results show significant improvement (about 25%) in parameter estimation when domain adaptation is applied, compared to models trained solely on simulations. Preliminary results applying SBI with neural posterior estimation in galaxy spectroscopy are also showing promising outcomes (e.g., [N. Candebat et al. 2024](#); [Bracci et al., in preparation](#)).

4. CONCLUSIONS

We argue that the integration of SBI with domain adaptation represents a powerful paradigm for scientific discovery across disciplines (e.g., [K. Cranmer et al. 2020](#)). Domain adaptation addresses the key challenge of bridging the gap between simulated and real data, allowing models trained on synthetic inputs to generalize effectively (e.g., [Y. Ganin et al. 2016](#); [M. Wang & W. Deng 2018](#)). When combined with neu-

ral posterior estimation, this approach also enables efficient inference with rigorous uncertainty quantification (e.g., [G. Papamakarios et al. 2021](#)). The case studies in astronomy demonstrate the practical benefits of this framework. Models trained on simulations can successfully analyze real observations (e.g., [F. Belfiore et al. 2025](#); [C. Bracci et al. 2025](#)), speed up preparation for new instruments (e.g., [M. Ginolfi et al. 2025](#)), and deliver reliable uncertainty estimates for complex parameters (e.g., [N. Candebat et al. 2024](#)). These capabilities are equally valuable in other fields, where similar challenges of limited labeled data and complex parameter spaces exist (e.g., [J. Brehmer 2021](#); [A. Wehenkel et al. 2023](#)). As simulation capabilities continue to advance, driven by increasing computational power and more sophisticated physical models, the alignment between virtual and real data will improve. Combined with ongoing developments in domain adaptation methodology, these advances promise to further enhance the reliability and impact of SBI.

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